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EDITORIAL (pp 76-82):

How Not to Investigate Scientific Misconduct and Fraud.

How Not to Investigator Scientific misconduct and Fraud is an editorial expose of undercounting of cases of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud, and why there is also an undercounting of retracted papers. There are a lot more papers floating in the scientific literature that ought to be retracted but are not. The author of this editorial has highlighted one paper in this issue of the Journal of Investigative Critique of Published Scientific Articles that contains several anomalous figures in it. The author of this editorial argues that in order to obtain a true figure of the number of problematic papers, one should pick a sufficiently large number of papers at random and determine how many among them should be retracted but are not.

Author: H.Y. Lim Tung, PH.D., Peptide and Protein Chemistry Research Laboratory, Nacbraht Biomedical Research Institute, 3164 21st Street, Suite 117, Astoria (NYC), NY 11106, USA. E mail: hyltung2010@nacbrahtbiomedresins.net

Many writers have commented on the fact that while there has been an increase of cases of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud, the total number of retracted papers compared to the total number of published Scientific Articles has remained low [1-3]. It has been estimated that in 2000, the retraction rate was 1.8 per 10,000 published papers and in 2015, it was 4 per 10,000 published papers. The absolute number of papers retracted from 2015 to 2018 were on average over 600 per year [3]. From 2010 to 2016, there were approximately 2.5 retracted papers per 10,000 published papers [2]. That number is somewhat misleading because there has not been a systematic study of actual numbers of problematic published Scientific Articles. What we know

concerns only those papers that have been retracted. What we do not know is how many problematic papers that should be retracted are not, and are still floating around and remain in the Scientific Literature. There has not been a systematic random study of published papers that should have been retracted but are not. In order to obtain a true figure of the number of problematic papers, one should pick a sufficiently large number of papers at random and determine how many among them should be retracted but are not. Most writers agree that Scientific Misconduct was the main cause for paper retractions [2,4].

The closest to a systematic random study of problematic papers is the one done by Bik et al. [5]. In the study, the authors papers exhaustively analyzed 20621 papers published between 1995 and 2014 in 40 different Scientific Journals for inappropriate Image Manipulation, and concluded that ~3.8 percent of the total papers that were systematically analyzed contained Inappropriate Image Manipulation. This figure is a lot higher than the papers that have been retracted. Bik et al. goes further as to suggest that as many as one out of every 25 papers contain unscientific and inappropriate Image Manipulation. In another study, Bik et al [6] suggest that "as many as 35,000 papers in the literature are candidates for retraction due to inappropriate image duplication. It is indeed quite alarming that Francis Collins, the Director of the US National Institutes of Health that oversees an annual budget of over \$30 billion in 2019, made the following statement in 2014: "Let's be clear: with rare exceptions, we have no evidence to suggest that irreproducibility is caused by scientific misconduct. In 2011, the Office of Research Integrity of the US Department of Health and Human Services pursued only 12 such cases³. Even if this represents only a fraction of the actual problem, fraudulent papers are vastly outnumbered by the hundreds of thousands published each year in good faith" [1]. The statement of Francis Collins indicates that he is living in a bubble. It is not clear whether he will stick to his statement that was made in 2014 after he reads the two papers of Bik et al [5,6].

A consistent and annoying problem is that Scientific Researchers rarely volunteer to retract their problematic papers. Only after their Scientific Papers are flagged by anonymous Fraud Busters who air their concerns in certain websites, including PUBPEER, that Principal Scientific Researchers react, and only after they have been investigated by their own Research Institutions and found to have committed Scientific Misconduct, do they retract their papers. In many cases, Retractions are done sua sponte by the management of the Scientific Journals that have published

the problematic papers. For example, the Scientific Journal Science has retracted the paper entitled "MAVS, cGAS and endogenous retroviruses in T independent B cell responses " authored by Zeng, M. et al [7] even though the first author refused to retract. Another example is the retraction of the paper entitled "Super Bowls: Serving Bowl Size and Food Consumption" authored by Wansink, B. and Cheney, M.M. and published in the Journal of American Medical Association [8]. In other cases, the Research Institutions at which the Scientific Misconduct took place contacted the Scientific Journals and requesting the Scientific Journals to retract those papers that they have found to contain Fabricated Data and Falsified Data as in the Matter of Harvard Medical School and Brigham and Women's Hospital v. Piero Anserva and Annarosa Leri [9,10].

There are also cases where the Principal Scientific Researchers of a problematic paper have sued the entity that highlighted the problematic paper in public to intimidate it from doing what the United States federal Court has called Freedom of Speech and Freedom to Publish. In the Matter of Fazlul Sarkar v. John and/or Jane Does(s) and PUBPEER et al. [11], the Presiding Judge of the Michigan Court of Appeals ruled that "individuals are entitled to make anonymous statements under the First Amendment, and the mere fact that someone later prints some of those anonymous statements and distributes them does not suddenly destroy that protection.

Another way at looking at the issue of undercounting the extent of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud is to analyze the number of False Claims Act lawsuits that Research Universities and other Research Institutions have to defend and either have to settle or have lost. The most recent sensational case but nevertheless illustrative of the masking of the true number of retracted papers associated with Scientific Misconduct and Fraud is in the Matter of United States ex rel. Thomas v. Duke University et al. [12,13] in which Duke University had to come to terms with the United States Department and was forced to pay the astronomical sum of U.S. 112.5 Million to settle False Claims Act allegations with respect to Scientific Research Misconduct and Scientific Fraud. What was mostly swept under the carpet is the charges that ex rel. Thomas levied against the Scientific Researchers, and Duke University. Because of the settlement, Duke University is most probably not going to pursue the allegations of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud that ex rel. Thomas proffered against Erin Potts-Kant, William Foster and Monica Kratt. Although William Foster was the Principal Scientific Researcher (i.e the Principal

Investigator) and Erin Potts-Kant was only a technician with a BS degree, somehow all the blame was put upon Erin Potts-Kant. What is even more troubling is that because of the settlement pursuant to the False Claims Act, no one will know how it is possible that the Principal Scientific Researcher, William Foster would not know that the technician was fabricating data and supplying him with Scientific Data that was too good to be true in order that he could use the said Fabricated Data to obtain millions of dollars under false pretense from the NIH and other US Governmental Agencies. Perhaps more puzzling is the fact that all the media, including the Scientific Journals, Science and Nature are talking about Erin Potts-Kant as if she was the Principal Scientific Researcher when she is only a technician. The Principal Scientific Researcher (i.e the Principal Investigator), William Foster, Duke University and the Officials at Duke University are the ones that should be saddled with the blame and not the technician, Erin Potts-Kant was never trained as a bona fide Scientific Researcher and never took any Graduate Courses in the Philosophy of Science and Scientific Ethics. When the whistleblower, ex rel. Thomas filed complaints about Scientific Misconduct through Data Fabrication at Duke University, the officials ignored him and made his stay at Duke University uncomfortable. He had no choice but to file a lawsuit under the False Claims Act. How is it possible that a technician like Erin Potts-Kant was allowed to command such a mounting presence in the running of a laboratory that extracted more than \$200 Million under false pretense from the US National Institutes of Health and US Environmental Protection Agency.

Another case that is worth mentioning with respect to the undercounting of cases of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud is the Matter of United States ex rel. Resnick v. Weill Medical College of Cornell University et al. [14,15] in the United States Court of the Southern District of New York. Ex rel. Resnick initially alleged that the Principal Scientific Researcher (i.e the Principal Investigator), Lorraine Gudas "misrepresented which researchers were working on particular grants; misapplied and fraudulently accounted for grant funds; falsified data from her research; and submitted the same projects multiple times, even if they had been funded by other grants,". However after Weill Medical College of Cornell University settled with the United States Attorney for

the Southern District and agreed to pay \$2,606,751 as fine for "failing to disclose the full extent of Guda's various active research projects", the questions of Data Falsification and the submission of Falsified Data by the Principal Scientific Researcher, Lorraine Gudas to the NIH and the US Department of Defense were quickly forgotten and filed in the drawer for good over the objection of ex rel. Resnick. In this case, the Research University chose to whitewash potential occurrence of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud that the Principal Scientific Researcher, Lorraine Gudas may have committed. Indeed, a representative of Weill Medical College of Cornell University stated the following: "All of the funded research in question was performed by Weill Cornell Medical College and resulted in numerous discoveries, publications and other contributions to the body of scientific and clinical knowledge. The government's claims did not relate to the quality or scientific integrity of the research" [15]. This is a typical example of how not to investigate Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud by a Research University.

In this author's opinion, there is no doubt that there is undercounting of the number of cases of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud, and the number of problematic papers that ought to be retracted but are not. A systematic random study of published scientific papers needs to be conducted in order to know the full extent of problematic papers that are floating in the Scientific Literature.

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